

EFFECT OF COMPLEMENTARY FERTILIZERS ON YIELD AND STORABILITY OF PUMPKIN ACCESSIONS IN NSUKKA

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ABSTRACT

RESEARCH ARTICLE

An experiment was conducted during 2025 cropping season at the Department of Crop Science Teaching and Research farm, University of Nigeria, Nsukka to determine the effect of complementary fertilizers on the yield and storability of pumpkin accessions. Treatments comprised of nine complementary fertilizers on the main plots and single row plots of five plants per accession of pumpkin on the sub-plots. The results revealed that Ugbogiri accession from Enugu State produced significantly ($p < 0.05$) highest number of fruits (3.72), highest number of seeds (117.10), heaviest seeds (6.51 kg), total seed yield (15.40 t ha⁻¹) and fruit yield of 19.33 t ha⁻¹. The heaviest fruits (4.84 kg) and longest fruits (28.06 cm) were recorded at Janadu accession. Percentage weight loss on pumpkin accessions at 12th weeks after storage were non-significant from the F-test. The yield and storability was significantly ($p < 0.05$) affected by complementary fertilizers except on fruit yield and initial fruit thickness. Plants subjected to 5 t/ha PGM augmented with NPK 15:15:15 (100 kg/ha) produced highest number of fruits/plant (3.88) and fruit yield of 19.88 t/ha. Plots with janadu accession treated with NPK 15:15:15 (200 kg/ha) gave higher seed yield. The application of complementary fertilizers should be adopted since it has huge potential to improve yield. For extended availability of fresh pumpkin fruits, esi 1, esi 2, ugbogiri and ugboma accessions cultivated with the application of complementary fertilizers should be encouraged since it has longer storage life than janadu accession from Cross-River State.

KEYWORDS: Accessions, pumpkin, complementary fertilizers, storability

INTRODUCTION

Pumpkin (*Cucurbita pepo* Linn.) are locally called “Enyu” in southeastern Nigeria belongs to the family Cucurbitaceae. The family is among the most important plant families supplying humans with edible products and useful fibers (Oloyede *et al.*, 2013). Its center of origin is Mexico, where it was domesticated at least 8,000 to 10,000 years (Smith, 1997). Pumpkin is adapted to a wide variety of soil types which have good drainage and slight acidity. Most species are monoecious with male and female flowers borne separately on the same plant (Aruah *et al.*, 2012). It is an important traditional food crop with high nutritional value, which can be consumed mature and immature (Oloyede, 2012).

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With the increasing pressure on farm land for infrastructural development and low soil fertility status of tropical soils, farmers are using low quantities of organic fertilizer due to their limited quantities despite government exertion to implement more sustainable agricultural practices by utilizing locally available inputs that are less deleterious to the environment (Rodrigo *et al.*, 2012). One way of increasing the nutrient status of soil is by boosting its soil content with the use of organic materials like poultry manure, animal waste and the use of compost or with the use of inorganic fertilizers (Dauda *et al.*, 2005). The application of manure fortified with inorganic fertilizer increases soil concentration of nutrients and organic matter and, also increases the soil availability of N, P and K (Soliman and Hossan, 2004; Eghball, 2002).

Pumpkin can be stored for a period of 1 - 3 months when matured and depends on many factors, such as cultivar, precipitation and temperature conditions during plant growing season, fertilization, time of harvesting and storage conditions (Arvayo-Ortiz *et al.*, 1994). They can be best stored at 12^oC - 15^oC and relative humidity of 50% - 70% (Boelema, 1981). However, there is also a challenge to improve storage potential of fruits. It has also reported that fertilizer application affects the storage behavior and quality of pumpkin but there is dearth of documented information regarding its soil nutrient requirement and storability that may be of help to these farmers in this zone. Thus, this study was conducted to determine the performance of complementary fertilizers usage on yield and storability of pumpkin accessions.

Materials and Methods

The experiment was conducted at the Teaching and Research Farm, Department of Crop Science, University of Nigeria, Nsukka (06^o52'N and longitude of 07^o24'E) Enugu State, Nigeria from May – November, 2025. The experimental site is characterized by sub-humid tropical conditions with bimodal annual rainfall distribution that ranges from 1500 mm – 2000 mm with a shift in the second peak of rainfall from September – October, a mean annual temperature of 29^oC and a relative humidity that ranges 69 - 80% (Uguru, 2011). Pumpkin accessions were collected from Ebonyi, Ekiti, Enugu, Cross River and Kogi States of Nigeria. The seeds were sourced owing to their abundant, popularity, productivity and high prospect of the crop in the area. After the collection, the accessions were first characterized according to local names, source/place of collections, local government area and State (Table 1).

The experimental treatments consisted of nine levels of complementary fertilizers (0 t/ha, 200 kg/ha NPK 15:15:15, 200 kg/ha NPK 20:10:10, 10 t/ha Poultry Manure (PM), 10 t/ha Pig Manure (PGM), 5 t/ha PM + NPK15:15:15 (100 kg/ha), 5 t/ha PM + NPK20:10:10 (100 kg/ha), 5 t/ha PGM + NPK 15:15:15 (100 kg/ha), 5 t/ha PGM + NPK 20:10:10 (100 kg/ha) and five accessions of pumpkin (esi1, esi 2, janadu, ugbogiri and ugboma). These were laid as a split plot design with four replications. The complementary fertilizers occupied the main plots while the pumpkin accessions were assigned to the sub plots. Each sub-plot has single row of five plants per accession of pumpkin with a total of 36 plots. Each plot measures 5 m x 4 m giving an area of 20 m². The field was well ploughed harrowed before sowing. The five accessions were sown in single row plot of five plants at spacing of 0.8 m x 1m and plant population of twenty-five stands per plot (12,500 stands/ha). Poultry and pig manures were cured and applied two weeks before planting and NPK fertilizers were applied two weeks after germination using side placement method to the plots allotted to them. Weeds, insects and pests were controlled when needed. Harvesting of pumpkin fruits were done when the fruits are matured.

Yield data were recorded from three sampling stands each on 5 accessions of pumpkin per sub-plot after harvest. The number of fruits per plant was counted and recorded at each harvest. Fruits weight (kg) was determined by weighing the number of fruits at each harvest and mean fruit weight was recorded. The fruit length was measured using a measuring tape at successive harvesting interval. Fruit yield (t/ha) was determined by summing up the successive harvesting intervals and expressed in t/ha. Number of seeds per sample were counted after seed extraction. Weight of dried seeds and 100-seed weight per sample were measured using analytical weighing balance in gram. Seed yield was determined by converting the weight of seeds per fruit to kilogram per hectare.

The pumpkin accessions (45) samples that are free from injury and bruises were harvested and stored in an improved ventilated barn with rat-proof netting. The stored pumpkin fruits were placed on wooden shelves. Dry and wet bulb thermometers were used in monitoring temperature and relative humidity twice daily at 10.00 am and 4.00 am. The average temperature for the morning and evening were 26.5 and 27.2⁰C, respectively, while the relative humidities were 76 and 78%. Monthly percentage weight loss was determined by

Monthly percentage weight loss = $(IW - CW)/IW * 100$, where, IW = initial weight of pumpkin fruits and CW = current weight of the pumpkin fruits. Fruit thickness was determined before and after storage using a pair of vernier caliper (cm).

Data collected were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) for split plot design procedure using Genstat statistical software (17th edition). Significant treatment means were separated using least significant Difference (LSD) at a 5% level of probability.

Results

Yield Traits of Pumpkin Accessions as Influenced by Complementary Fertilizers

The results of the analysis of variance showed that accessions had highly significant ($P = 0.01$) effect on the yield attributes assessed. The results showed that Ugbogiri accession had the highest mean number of fruits/plant of approximately (4) fruits, number of seeds (117.10), weight of dried seeds (6.51 g), total seed yield (15.40 kg/ha) and fruit yield of 19.33 t/ha which differed significantly from other accessions. The accession, Janadu had fruit weight and longest fruits of 4.84 kg and 28.06 cm, respectively when compared to other accessions (Table 2). Janadu, Ugboma and Esi 1 accessions with values 64.2 g, 4.15 g and 9.70 kg ha, respectively, gave least number of seeds, weight of dried seeds and total seed yield.

Application of complementary fertilizer significantly ($p < 0.05$) influenced yield of pumpkin as shown in Table 2. It resulted that 200 kg/ha NPK (15:15:15) had higher number of seeds, 100-seed weight, weight of dried seeds and seed yield with respective values 196.60, 6.40 g, 14.98 g and 37.46 kg/ha when compared with other fertilizer values recorded. The application of 5 t/ha PGM + 100 kg/ha NPK (15:15:15) produced the highest number of fruits of 4 fruits, which differed from the mean number of fruits/plant produced by no fertilizer plots, 200 kg/ha NPK (15:15:15) and 5 t/ha PGM + 100 kg/ha NPK (20:10:10). The application of complementary fertilizers, 10 t/ha PM, produced the heaviest fruit of 4.85 kg. However, 5 t/ha PM + 100 kg/ha NPK (20:10:10) produced longest fruits of 23.15 cm when compared to control plots. The complementary fertilizers was not significant on the fruit yield from the F-test. The biplot (Fig. 1) revealed that Janadu accession grown with PM application at 10 t/ha produced heaviest fruits of 7.28 kg. The biplot in figure 2 of the interaction effect of accessions and complementary fertilizer application of the seed quality revealed that Janadu

accession treated with 200 kg/ha NPK (15:15:15) produced more number of seeds, highest 100-seed weight, weight of dried seeds and total seed yield.

Effect of Accessions and Complementary Fertilizer Application on Storability of Pumpkin

The results in table 3 showed that there were highly significant differences ($p < 0.001$) among the accessions, complementary fertilizer and their interactions on the initial pumpkin weight, fruit thickness and weight loss of fruit across weeks observed except at 12 weeks of storage among accessions were they are statistically the same from the f-test. The weight loss of fresh pumpkin fruits across the weeks accessed with respective values of 5.94, 6.25 and 8.99% were highest in the accession, Janadu, which differed significantly from other accession weight loss recorded at different weeks. The fruits produced by Janadu accession cannot be stored for longer period of time. The accessions, Ugbogiri and Esi 1, had the thickest fruit of 13.18 cm and 8.42 cm thickness after 3 months storage, respectively, which differed significantly from other accessions used. Application of 200 kg/ha NPK (20:10:10), 10 t/ha PGM and no fertilizer plots had highest fresh pumpkin weight loss of 3.33, 5.68 and 11.99% at 4th, 8th and 12th week, respectively, which differed significantly when compared to the least weight loss across weeks stored. NPK (15:15:15) at rates of 200 kg/ha produced 10.92 cm fruit thickness when compared to other thickness on other complemented fertilizers used while ^{PM} at 5 t/ha + 100 kg/ha of NPK (15:15:15) recorded the least fruit thickness of 3.82 cm. The biplot in figure 3 shows the interaction of accessions and complementary fertilizers on the weight loss and fruit thickness of fresh pumpkin fruits. Esi 2-4 (Esi 2 accession integrated with 10 t/ha PGM, Ugbogiri-1 (Ugbogiri accession without fertilizer) and Ugboma-1 (Ugboma accession without fertilizer) showed highly significant differences with the highest weight loss of pumpkin fruits at 12 week of storage. Ugbo-5 (Ugbogiri accession at PGM at 5 t/ha and 100 kg/ha of NPK (15:15:15) produced thickest fruits which showed highly significant differences among others. Jana-3 (Janadu accession at 200 kg/ha NPK (20:10:10) produced fruits that have highest fruit thickness after three months of storage that differed among other.

Discussion

Effect of Accessions and Complementary Fertilizer Application on Fruit Yield of Pumpkin

The variability observed in the yield traits in the study may be linked to the genetic makeup of the accessions. Ugbogiri accession from Enugu State produced highest number of fruits, number of seeds, weight of dried seeds, seed yield and fruit yield. On the other hand, accession, Janadu produced heaviest and longest fruits. This is in consonance with the report of Aruah *et al.* (2012) who observed genetic differences in growth and yield of ten genotypes of pumpkin. The result is also in agreement with the report of Afangideh and Uyoh (2007), Ene *et al.* (2016) who found that genetic variation existed among cucumber genotypes.

Number of fruits and fruit yield significantly increased with the application of 5 t/ha PGM + 100 kg/ha NPK (15:15:15). Plots with no fertilizer gave least yield attributes. This reduction in yield is as a result of insufficient nutrient in the soil. When optimum nutrients are applied, it results to production of high quality and better nutritive plants (Eremrena and Coleman, 2025; Baiyeri *et al.*, 2009). The higher number of fruits, heaviest fruits and longer fruits were significantly produced by the application of complementary fertilizers when compared to no fertilizer was applied. This corroborates the report by Anjanappa *et al.* (2012) that cucumber fruits respond positively to integrated fertilizer application. Complementary fertilizer

applications enhanced the seed quality of pumpkin as obtained in the work. Generally, plants grown with 200 kg/ha NPK (15:15:15) performed better than other complementary fertilizers used in terms of pumpkin seed quality measured. NPK fertilizer is an important factor for vigorous growth due to its immediate availability to the plant roots and increased plant yield (Mohamed *et al.*, 2012). Interaction of Janadu accession from Cross River State that received 100 kg/ha NPK (15:15:15) had more pumpkin yield. This observation was probably a reflection of the distinctive genotypic response pattern to the prevailing environmental cues.

Effect of Accessions and Complementary Fertilizer Applications Storability Qualities of pumpkin

The physiological loss in weight of pumpkin accessions fruits is an economic loss to farmers in the developed countries, since they sell the fruit by measures of its weight. In this study, the maximum weight loss was 8.99% after 90 days of storage was found at Janadu accession. This loss in weight and thickness might also be due to loss of moisture from fruit stalk. Janadu accession fruits easily spoil which significantly abridge the market value of these crop. The loss in weight of these stored pumpkin fruits may probably be due to the processes of respiration. Arvayo Oritz *et al.* (1994) reported that type of cultivars affects storability of pumpkin fruits. The reduction in weight loss observed in Esi 1 accession from Ekiti State can be associated with the relative humidity within the storage area as it help reduce transpiration from the produce. Complementary fertilizer applications influenced percentage weight loss. No fertilizer applications increased weight loss compared with the other treatments. Weight loss of stored pumpkins was affected by complementary fertilizer applications and the accessions of pumpkin. Fertilized Janadu pumpkin fruits had the highest percentage weight loss. This may be as a result of high fat content found on the accession which causes rancidity and exhibited highest severity of decay.

Conclusion

Ugbogiri accession had higher number of fruits (3.72), fruit yield (18.33 t/ha), number of seeds (117.10), highest weight of dried seeds (6.51 g) and total seed yield of 15.40 t/ha than other accession used. Janadu accession produced the heaviest fruits (4.84 kg) and longest fruits (28.06 cm) of pumpkin. Application of complementary fertilizer, 5 t/ha PGM + 100 kg/ha NPK (15:15:15) gave highest number of fruits and fruit yield of pumpkin with respective values of 3.88 and 19.88 t/ha. However, 200 kg/ha NPK (15:15:15) produced highest seed yield qualities of pumpkin. Esi 1, Esi 2 and Ugbogiri accessions had a better storage-life irrespective of whether treated with single fertilizer or complementary. Therefore, the cultivation of pumpkin accessions with the application of complementary fertilizers should be adopted since it has huge potential to improve yield, has longer storage life and better storage.

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Table 1. List of Accessions and Collection Areas

S/N	Local Names	Acronyms	Source/Place of Collection	LGA	States
1	Janadu	Jana	Ugep	Yakur	Cross-River
2	Ugboma	Ugboma	Omege	Abakaliki	Ebonyi
3	Esi	Esi 1	Ise-Ekiti	Orun	Ekiti
4	Ugbogiri	Ugbo	Enugu-Ezike	Igboeze-South	Enugu
5	Esi	Esi 2	Iyamuye	Ijumu	Kogi

Table 2: Main Effects of Accessions and Complementary Fertilizers on Fruit Yield Parameters of Pumpkin

Treatments	NF	WF	LF	FY	NS	100SW	WDS	SY
Accessions								
Esi1	3.19	3.94	18.98	16.00	77.4	3.98	4.27	9.70
Esi 2	2.83	3.72	18.28	14.72	97.1	3.71	5.15	12.90
Janadu	2.64	4.84	28.06	13.89	64.2	1.81	5.69	14.30
Ugbogiri	3.72	4.07	19.39	19.33	117.1	3.52	6.51	15.40
Ugboma	3.03	3.68	18.76	15.90	66.9	3.07	4.15	10.40
LSD_{0.05}	0.36	0.19	2.21	2.80	0.90	0.14	0.04	1.06
Complementary Fertilizers								
No fertilizer (0 t/ha)	2.25	3.02	14.59	12.52	190.4	5.55	10.26	24.28
NPK 15:15:15 (200 kg/ha)	2.93	4.25	22.30	13.88	196.6	6.40	14.98	37.46
NPK 20:10:10 (200 kg/ha)	3.28	3.94	18.96	14.75	95.6	3.60	5.16	12.90
PM (10 t/ha)	3.23	3.99	18.99	19.12	42.0	2.34	2.40	6.01
PGM (5 t/ha)/NPK 15:15:15 (100 kg/ha)	3.88	4.25	21.98	19.88	16.0	1.11	1.11	2.77
PGM (5 t/ha)/NPK 20:10:10 (100 kg/ha)	2.63	4.12	21.23	14.30	49.4	2.94	3.31	8.30
PM (10 t/ha)	3.20	4.85	21.99	16.12	73.2	3.25	4.69	11.73
PM (5 t/ha)/NPK 15:15:15 (100 kg/ha)	3.10	4.09	23.00	16.62	26.2	1.42	1.42	1.75
PM(5 t/ha)/NPK 20:10:10 (100 kg/ha)	3.28	3.97	23.15	14.62	71.6	2.34	3.04	7.61
LSD_{0.05}	0.65	0.44	3.66	NS	1.21	0.19	0.19	1.42

NF = Number of Fruits, FWF = Fresh Weight of Fruits (kg), FL = Fruit Length (cm), FY = Fruit Yield (t/ha), NS = Number of Seed, 100SW = 100 Seed Weight (g), WDS = Weight of Dried Seed (g) and SY = Seed Yield (t/ha)

Table 3: Main Effects of Accessions and Complementary Fertilizer Application on Storability Qualities of Pumpkin Fruits

Treatments	% Weight Loss in Weeks				
	4	8	12	IFT	FT
Accessions					
Esi1	0.00	1.49	7.70	10.29	8.42
Esi 2	2.03	3.49	8.64	10.88	8.00
Janadu	5.94	6.25	8.99	11.06	2.76
Ugbogiri	0.26	4.95	8.73	13.18	7.51
Ugboma	0.11	1.60	8.83	10.44	6.36
LSD_{0.05}	0.159	1.791	N.S	1.427	0.239
Complementary Fertilizers					
No fertilizer (0 t/ha)	1.00	2.79	11.99	10.63	9.33
NPK 15:15:15 (200 kg/ha)	1.00	2.43	8.00	11.77	10.92
NPK 20:10:10 (200 kg/ha)	3.33	4.39	5.84	9.66	7.98
PM (10 t/ha)	3.13	5.68	10.14	11.30	4.04
PGM (5 t/ha)/NPK 15:15:15 (100 kg/ha)	3.09	4.63	7.28	11.68	4.62
PGM (5 t/ha)/NPK 20:10:10 (100 kg/ha)	0.69	4.09	9.62	10.70	6.04
PM (10 t/ha)	0.69	1.59	8.62	12.10	6.06
PM (5 t/ha)/NPK 15:15:15 (100 kg/ha)	1.40	2.95	8.11	11.32	3.82
PM(5 t/ha)/NPK 20:10:10 (100 kg/ha)	0.69	3.68	7.59	11.36	6.68
LSD_{0.05}	0.213	2.402	2.462	NS	0.320

IFT- Initial fruit thickness (cm), FT- fruit thickness (cm) after storage

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Figure 1: A biplot showing combined effects of accessions and complementary fertilizers application on yield traits of the pumpkin. Yield trait codes: NF/PL – Number of fruits per plant, FRWF/PL – Fresh weight of fruits per plant, FC – Fruit circumference, FL – Fruit length, FY – Fruit yield. Accessions: as seen in Table 1. Complementary fertilizers 1-9 as arranged in Table 2.

